

A small contribution to the Voynich Manuscript research

Jonas Tokarsky

1. Introduction

Since its discovery by Wilfrid M. Voynich in 1912 in Italy [1], the manuscript written in an unknown script, called the Voynich Manuscript after its discoverer (officially the Beinecke MS 408 [2]), has been a challenge not only for scientists of various fields, but also for amateur researchers.

It is almost certain that the Voynich manuscript (further denoted only as MS) is not a modern forgery [3] and that it was written in the 15th century. According to radiocarbon dating, the creation of the parchment can be dated to 1404-1438 [4]. The known history of the MS is provided in many sources [5-8], only the basic facts are listed here: (1) in the first half of the 17th century, the MS was located in the Kingdom of Bohemia, most likely in Prague; (2) in 1665 (or 1666) the MS was sent to Athanasius Kircher in Rome, Italy; (3) in the 18th and 19th century the MS was most likely the property of the Jesuit order; (4) in 1912 the MS was found by Voynich in Villa Mondragone in Frascati (today a suburb of Rome); (5) in 1969 the MS becomes a property of Yale University in USA.

Structure of the MS and its external characteristics are also the subject of many studies, only the basic facts are listed here: (1) the MS is divided into several parts: botanical, astronomical (astrological), cosmological, zodiac, biological (balneological), pharmaceutical, pure textual (recipes) [4, 9]; (2) in addition to the text, the MS contains a large number of colored drawings; (3) the MS is not complete, some folios are missing [10]; (4) the folios of the MS are not in the original order [4,11,12].

The MS is written in an unknown script (generally called Voynichese) containing approximately 22-26 characters [13-15]. Taking into account combined characters and special, rarely appearing, characters, this number can be even higher [15]. According to the frequency of occurrence of characters, groups of characters and words, two languages called Language A and Language B are distinguished in the MS [4,6,16,17]. Although obeying the Zipf's law [18-20], the text of the MS is conspicuously repetitive, e.g. *qokedy qokedy dal qokedy qokedy* (5th line in f78r), *qokedy qokedy qokedy* (13th line in right part of f75r), *qokeedy qokeedy qokedy*

qokedy qokeedy (9th line from the bottom in f75r) or *daiin daiin daiin* (line 3 in f89r2). Also some characters in words are repeated three to four times in a row, e.g. *deeeese* (2nd paragraph, line 3, f7r) or *keees* (line 3 in f21v), and the length of the words seems to be a descriptor of their position in the text [21]. This led to the conclusions that it is a cipher [22] or an elaborate hoax [19,23,24]. However, other researchers believe that the MS is written in a natural language, be it Arabic [25], Hebrew [26-28], proto-Romance [29], Turkish [30], Latin [31], etc. Possible reasons for the failures to date in understanding the text of the MS are widely discussed by Stephen Bax [32], François Parmentier [33], or Adam Lewis [34], to name a few. Although many words have been written on this topic, the problem can be summarized very briefly: when one does not know either the language or the script and only one text is available, there is nothing to grasp [4]. If this is the case, then one of the ways to approach the text is to start from assumptions, i.e. to establish a hypothesis and see where it leads. Studying the text as a whole by computational linguistic methods is undoubtedly interesting, but none of such studies has yet led to the translation of even a single word. The results of these studies only show that the MS carries some information – that it is highly likely to be meaningful [8,35-37]. Partial evidence suggesting that MS may not be meaningless gibberish is not a negligible result. But it is also not enough. Present work is therefore based on assumptions, and the assumptions are as follows: (1) The text of the MS is meaningful. (2) The original text is Latin. (3) Images refer to text. (4) Image captions correspond to what is shown. (5) Encoding of the text is not algorithmizable.

We consider the last assumption to be particularly important. In our opinion, the search for a comprehensive and unified procedure, which, by applying it to an open text using a set of characters, will produce Voynichese, is a dead end. The author of the MS surely could have created such a procedure. The author of the MS could have been one of the most ingenious cryptographers of all time. However, from the probability point of view, it seems to be a more acceptable assumption that the unbreakability of the "cipher" is due to the internal inconsistency of "encryption" rather than the invention of incredible ingenious method. Let us recall here the words of Nick Pelling, who wrote in a discussion with his readers on June 16, 2013 [7]: *It is relatively easy to devise a plausible decryption for a few words of the Voynich, extraordinarily hard to sustain one for a whole page, excruciatingly hard to do the same for the entire manuscript.*

In our opinion, the same words in the MS can be written differently, some words can actually be acronyms, some words can be written backwards, some words can be anagrams - this assumption could explain the failures of understanding the MS so far. There is a valid objection

that one can decipher anything in any way with this assumption. However, the fact remains that there is no argument against the possibility that the author of the MS used just such inconsistent "encryption".

Can we completely rule out the possibility that the MS was readable only by an initiated reader? Initiated not in the sense of knowing the "cipher", but in the sense of receiving the author's explanation of the content of various parts of the text. Some lines / some words would thus be a kind of mnemonic aid. Every other reader in line would then have to go through the oral explanation from someone who had already gone through it before. The very fact that the text is not open suggests the author's need to hide its content. Hiding behind a consistent cipher describable by a series of successive steps is not without the danger that the cipher will be broken and the text can be read by anyone. However, if the understanding of the text is conditioned by a personal explanation, we get the image of a kind of initiation. This leads to the idea, not *a priori* excludable, of a secret society, order, or family (see also [38]), where one can expect strong ties of the individual to this community and thus perhaps a reduced probability of disclosing the contents of the MS to persons outside this community. The reader may think at this point that we have let the imagination run wild perhaps too much. However, imagination is very useful when we know that we know nothing. Which in the case of the MS is a description of the situation in a nutshell.

This work is focused mainly on figures captions with the aim to show that the aforementioned assumptions lead to meaningful results. Using the captions of some figures, an attempt is made to determine the meaning of at least some characters. Captions of figures were chosen for the reason that the incompleteness of the MS and the non-original arrangement of the folios do not affect them. Moreover, a direct connection to a specific image can serve as a guide to understanding the meaning of the words in caption, rather than in the case of the main text, where the connection to a specific image is not so obvious, especially if there are more images on a given folio. Correctness of determining the meaning of some characters is further tested by estimating the possible forms of a specific word that should occur abundantly in the botanical section, and by monitoring the number of occurrences of these forms in the MS.

EVA transcription [15,35] is used in this work.

2. Identification of characters in Voynichese

2.1. Seven stars on f68r3

The f68r3 contains one of the few pictures whose interpretation is almost universally agreed [5,27,32,39-42]: the seven stars in the constellation of the Pleiades (Fig. 1)¹.

Fig. 1. Detail of f68r3 with seven stars. Credit: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Yale University.

Let's focus on two labels - "doaro" to the right of the stars² and "oalcheol" under the curve connecting the seven stars with the central circle (part of the circle is visible in the lower right corner of Fig. 1).

It has been suggested earlier the label of the seven stars may mean "taurus" [32,39,44,45]. However, it is more likely that the label "doaro" refers directly to the constellation of Pleiades and that it is their alternative name. Reading backwards and assuming that "d" and "r" in Voynichese actually match "d" and "r" in Latin, we get the word "oraod". The Pleiades were Oreads [46]. The characters "d" and "r" in Voynichese will continue to be considered "d" and "r" in Latin, bearing in mind that this may not be the only meaning and that the characters "d" and "r" in Voynichese may also represent other letters in Latin, e.g. "d" in Voynichese may represent also "t" in Latin.

¹ Some researchers accept this interpretation with reservations [43].

² Although Stephen Bax [32] used Grove's transcription "doary", the author of this text believes that Stolfi's transcription "doaro" is more correct [44].

The characters "o" and "a" in Voynichese will continue to be considered vowels in Latin.

In his extensive study of stars labels, Stephen Bax compiled a table of 64 labels from f68r1, f68r2, f68r3 and attempted to interpret them [47]. However, the label "oalcheol" was not included in the list, probably because it belongs to the curve leading to the stars, not the stars themselves. Nevertheless, the author of this text believes that the label "oalcheol" is important. It contains seven characters, a number equal to the number of stars. This interesting coincidence suggests that "oalcheol" could be an abbreviation from initials. The names of the seven Oreads (stars in the constellation) listed alphabetically are as follows: Alcyone, Asterope, Celaeno, Electra, Maia, Merope, and Taygete [48]. Three of these names begin with a vowel (Asterope, Alcyone, Electra) and three vowel characters ("o", "a", "o") are present in "oalcheol". Two of the three names begin with the same vowel (Asterope, Alcyone), and two of the three vowel characters are the same ("o"). This is interesting correlation. Two of these names begin with M (Maia, Merope) and two identical characters ("l") are present in "oalcheol". Another interesting correlation.

The names Celaeno and Taygete remain for the characters "e" and "ch".

This solution seems simpler and more straightforward than the previously proposed hypothesis that it is an anagram of the single name Alcyone [49]. In addition, this solution eliminates the problem of why the character "l" in Voynichese should once represent "l" and once "n" in Latin ("l" – "l" and at the same time "eol" – "one", see [49]). The proposed meaning of "oalcheol" is also not dependent on whether the label of the stars is rather "doaro" or "doary".

In the label "oalcheol", the character "ch" is the only character consisting of two characters also appearing separately in the MS (transcribed as "c" and "h").³ It is also the only character into which some other characters are "inserted" creating the so called "pedestalled gallows"⁴ ("cph", "cfh", "cth", "ckh" [8,50]). Last but not least, it is a character occurring in the most frequent words of the MS [8,20]. For the above reasons, determining its meaning is very important. There are several options.

1) It is a single character (e.g. "c" or "t"), however, this option is unlikely due to the possibility of splitting into two separate characters ("c" and "h").

³ *D'Imperio's suggestion that e.g. "a" could be composed of "e" and "i" [5] (later elaborated by Cham in the so-called curve-line system [51]) seems very unlikely to the author.*

⁴ *One can also meet the term "benched gallows" [51].*

- 2) It is a syllable (e.g. "ce" or "ta"), generally "consonant+vowel", however, the option "vowel+consonant" cannot be ruled out either.
- 3) It is a combination of the two previous options.
- 4) The character "ch" has a completely different meaning than its separately written parts "c" and "h".

The following assignment of characters can be assumed.

Voynichese	Latin
o	a (generally a vowel)
a	e (generally a vowel)
l	m
ch	c, t, ce, ta (generally consonant+vowel)
e	c, t
d	d, t
r	r

The opinion that "o" and "a" in Voynichese represent vowels in Latin has already been presented by several researchers [26,29,32,52,53], so it is not a new idea. The most valuable result is the assumption that the character "l" in Voynichese could represent "m" in Latin.

2.2. Water on f78r

The label at the bottom of the f78r consists of a single word "okaral" (Fig. 2) and contains one unknown character "k". The words "aluarum" (belly, stomach, paunch [54]) or "aquarem" (water, lake, spa [55]) can be assumed, both of which make sense in the context of the figure - women have big bellies and stand in some tank with (very likely) liquid (Fig. 2)⁵.

We will assume that the character "k" in Voynichese is "l" or "q" in Latin. We will also keep in mind that in this case, two vowels in Latin ("ua") are represented by a single character in Voynichese ("a" in this case). This way of writing is not entirely incredible and can be accepted as possible – a single vowel character in Voynichese could represent a cluster of multiple vowels in Latin.

⁵ However, "okaral" = "aquarem" is more probable, since a very similar word ("okaran") is found on f67v2 below a square shape (in the middle of the folio) that is filled with a color similar to the color of the liquid in which the women stand on the f78r.

Fig. 2. Detail of f78r with the label "okaral" in the upper right corner. Credit: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Yale University.

The following assignment of characters can be assumed.

Voynichese	Latin
o	a (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
a	e (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
l	m
ch	c, t, ce, ta (generally consonant+vowel)
e	c, t
d	d, t
r	r
k	q, l

2.3. Other objects on f78r

Two objects are drawn at the top of f78r (the upper left and right corners of Fig. 3). It is not clear what these objects represent. It can be clouds, mushrooms, fruits (e.g. grapes or cones), but also canopies or muqarnas (see similarities to f75v and f84r). Each of the objects is assigned a label. The label on the left is "okchldlo", the label on the right is "okchdy". The most noticeable visual differences between the two objects are the dots on the "scales" of the right object (dots are missing on the left object) and the cross/orb on top of the left/right object, respectively (for the cross/orb, see f75v).

The right object label ("okchdy") appears as a shortened version of the left object label ("okchldlo") with "y" instead of "ldlo". Let's assume that the character "y" in Voynichese is a substitute character representing any set of characters⁶. This assumption can be supported by

⁶ The character "y" being an abbreviation character is not a new idea. D'Imperio mentioned it more than fifty years ago (p. 26 in [5]). See also Zandbergen's web page [50].

the similarity of the character "y" with so called abbreviation characters as listed by Capelli [56].

From the bottom of both objects comes something like a stream of liquid that passes through the hollow cylindrical segments. These segments look like cans and are very similar to those from which the human figures emerge on f70v2. Two of these cylindrical segments on f78r are labeled: the segment with two streams above and one below is labeled "daralocfhy", the segment directly above the pool with women is labeled "dchedaly" (right side of Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Detail of f78r with the labels "daralocfhy" and "dchedaly" in the right. Credit: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Yale University.

The label "daralocfhy" could stand for "diremptio" (separation [57]), "diremptus" (divide, separate [58]), "diremptis" (divided, separated [59]) etc., which makes sense given that this is a single segment with two streams.

The "daral-" would therefore mean "direm-", which is not inconsistent with the assumed meaning of the characters. Let's consider the last character "y" as an abbreviation character representing e.g. "-io", "-us" or "-is". The "cfh" would stand for "pt" (where "f" in Voynichese is "p" in Latin and "ch" in Voynichese is "t" in Latin).

Assuming "daralocfh-" matches "dirempt-", the character "o" is not in place of a vowel. So it is either extra or its placement has another reason, e.g. indication of the meaning of "cfh". It cannot be ruled out that the character "ch" represents several letters in Latin (e.g. both "t" and "c", possibly others). Together with the inserted character, this creates various possible combinations. It can therefore be expected that Voynichese has some way of indicating the exact meaning of the pedestalled gallows in a particular word.

The following assignment of characters can be assumed.

Voynichese	Latin
o	a (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
a	e (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
l	m
ch	c, t, ce, ta (generally consonant+vowel)
e	c, t
d	d, t
r	r
k	q, l
y	abbreviation character
f	p

2.4. Pleiades on f68r3

Let us go back to the f68r3. It is reasonable to assume that the word Pleiades should appear on this folio. If the word is not found near the drawing of the seven stars, it may be because it is found elsewhere, and the most likely place of occurrence is at the other end of the curve connecting the seven stars with the central circle. This is where the word "otchody" is found (see lower right corner of Fig. 1). Considering the assumed meaning of the characters, this word can be transcribed as follows:

"o"	"t"	"ch"	"o"	"d"	"y"
vowel	?	consonant	vowel	d/t	abbreviation
		+vowel			

Let's make three assumptions now.

- 1) The character "t" in Voynichese is "l" in Latin.
- 2) Meaning of the character "ch" in Voynichese is expanded with the possibility that it is a "vowel+vowel" in Latin.
- 3) The character "o" in Voynichese, if it stands before a consonant, does not have to be only a vowel, but can also represent a consonant. In this particular case: "ot"= "pl".

So the transcription could be as follows:

"ot"	"ch"	"o"	"d"	"y"
pl	ei	a	d	es

The author is aware of the boldness of the third assumption in particular. However, as will be shown in the 2.5. section, this third assumption will lead to a meaningful result in another case as well.

The following assignment of characters can be assumed.

Voynichese	Latin
o	a (generally a vowel or multiple vowels), consonant if standing before consonant
a	e (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
l	m
ch	c, t, ce, ta (generally consonant+vowel), vowel+vowel
e	c, t
d	d, t
r	r
k	q
y	abbreviation character
f	p
t	l

The hypothesis that "otchody" means Pleiades is supported by the occurrence of this word on f71v (astronomical section) where the Taurus zodiac sign is found.

2.5. Elements on f77r

Fig. 4. Drawing at the top of f77r. Credit: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Yale University.

The drawing at the top of f77r (Fig. 4) undoubtedly depicts the four Aristotelian elements – air, water, fire, earth (aer, aqua, ignis, terra in Latin) - as stated by SantaColoma over a decade ago [60]. SantaColoma correctly identified (from left to right) air, water, fire, and earth at each mouth of the tube. Nothing comes out of the middle mouth of the tube. This interpretation of the drawing has been accepted by several authors [61,62], but to the best of our knowledge, no

one has added any further information to it, although it seems to be another drawing (along with the Pleiades on f68r3), whose meaning is unquestionable, and which therefore forms a solid starting point in the search for the meaning and content of the text.⁷

Each of the four elements is formed by combining two of the four principles: moisture, dryness, heat and coldness. Air is moist and hot, water is moist and cold, fire is dry and hot, earth is dry and cold. On f77r, air and water on the left are separated from fire and earth on the right by the empty mouth of the tube (Fig. 4). It is interesting that the pairs of elements do not correspond to the distribution according to the alchemical theory of Sulphur and Mercury (fire and air for Sulphur, water and earth for Mercury [63]), yet the following parallel can be found. Air and water share the principle of moisture, and this principle belongs to Mercury (the feminine principle) - see the figure of the female (breasts, large buttocks, long hair) on the left. Fire and earth share the principle of dryness that can be assigned to Sulphur (masculine principle) - see the figure of the male (no breasts, small buttocks, shorter hair) on the right. Personifications of Mercury and Sulfur as female and male (usually as the White Queen and Red King) can be found in many alchemical paintings [64-67].

The theory of Sulphur and Mercury reached Europe with the Latin writings of Pseudo-Geber at the beginning of the 14th century (the *Summa perfectionis magisterii* describing the theory was written in the year ~1300 A.D. [68-70]). Some authors have a different opinion and move the origin of the theory back several hundred years [71]. So the theory may be older, but whether or not, the essential fact is that it cannot be newer. With regard to dating the age of the parchment (1404-1438 [4]), the author of the MS may have been familiar with the theory, as the theory had already been known in Europe at the time of production of the parchment (and thus also at the time of the creation of the MS, which could only be written after the production of the parchment). This is strong argument for the assumption that the drawing at the top of f77r is inspired by alchemy.

The assignment of labels to specific places on the drawing seems ambiguous at first glance, but if the right-left symmetry of the drawing is taken into account, then the female on the left has the upper label "darchdar" and the lower label "olkchs", the male on the right has the upper label "dotedy" and the lower label "soral" (see black arrows in Fig. 4). There is also the possibility that the lower labels "olkchs" and "soral" belong to the mouths of the tube into which the figures are sticking their hands. In that case, only the upper labels "darchdar" and "dotedy" would belong to the female and male figure, respectively.

⁷ Hypothesis that the images in the manuscript have no relation to the content of the text [33] seems unlikely to the author.

The remaining four labels belongs to the elements: "otedy" for air (aer), "otork" for water (aqua), "otol" for fire (ignis), "dchdy" for earth (terra). See white arrows in Fig. 4. The middle empty mouth of the tube has no label and most likely corresponds to the quintessence (quinta essentia, i.e. the fifth essence). The concept and idea of quintessence was already well known at the time of the creation of the MS. Aristotle (384-322 BC) introduced it in *De Caelo* [72]: "Ex quibus perspicuum est, naturam quadam esse corporis praeter eas quae hic sunt, quae his omnibus et diviniore sit, et prior." ("These premises clearly give the conclusion that there is in nature some bodily substance other than the formations we know, prior to them all and more divine than they." [73]).

Also, authors closer in time to the MS, Raymondus Lullus (Ramon Llull, 1232-1316 AD) and Johannes Ruspecissa (Jean de Roquetaillade, ~1310 – ~1368 AD), to name a few, wrote about quintessence in *Liber de secretis naturae seu de quinta essentia* and *Liber de Consideratione Quintae Essentiae*, respectively.

If the author of the MS wanted to keep the content of the text secret and chose a cryptic font for that reason, the labels in this drawing must have posed a serious problem. Since it is quite evident that the drawing depicts four elements, this is a place where the cryptic script can be broken very easily. We have no idea for what reason the author of the MS could not avoid this drawing and why he created it including labels. The fact remains that he did not avoid the drawing, that he created it and that he attached the labels. Labels therefore had to be encrypted especially carefully. There could be a change in the order of characters, a deliberate use of wrong characters, it is even possible that these labels have no meaning, that they are just a random jumble of letters to confuse the uninitiated reader. Nevertheless, although the labels obviously do not correspond to the words aer, aqua, ignis and terra, some indications can be found that the labels are meaningful.

The air is labeled "otedy", which can be transcribed as follows:

"o"	"t"	"e"	"d"	"y"
vowel	l	c/t	d/t	abbreviation

Let's make the assumption that the "e" in this case represents a vowel, not a c/t⁸.

⁸ It is certainly strange to make the assumption that a character that has been considered a consonant can also represent a vowel. However, the character "e" is very strange in itself. It occurs three times or four times in a row, words containing "eee" and "eeee" occur in the manuscript 395 times and 14 times, respectively. This way the character "e" deviates from the behaviour of normal letters and is much more like a substituting character that can represent any letter.

The transcription could then be as follows:

"o"	"t"	"e"	"d"	"y"
o	l	a	t	us

Let us recall the assumption that a single vowel character in Vonichese could represent a cluster of multiple vowels in Latin (see section 2.2.). Here we have the word "uolatus" in Latin, i.e. fly [74], which is not entirely out of the question when it comes to air.

The water is labelled "otork", which can be transcribed as follows:

"o"	"t"	"o"	"r"	"k"
vowel	l	vowel	r	q

If we move the "t" and "k" to other positions, we get the following

"t"	"o"	"k"	"o"	"r"
l	i	q	uo	r

Let us recall the assumption that a single vowel character in Vonichese could represent a cluster of multiple vowels in Latin (see section 2.2.). Here we have the word "liquor" in Latin, i.e. fluid, liquid [75], which is not entirely out of the question when it comes to water.

The fire is labelled "otol", which can be transcribed as follows:

"o"	"t"	"o"	"l"
vowel	l	vowel	m

Let us recall the assumption that if the character "o" stands before a consonant, it does not have to be only a vowel, but can also represent a consonant (see section 2.4.). The transcription could then be as follows:

"ot"	"o"	"l"
fl	a	m

This is not the whole word, just its beginning, but there is a striking connection with the words flamma, i.e. flame [76], flammeus, i.e. flaming [77], etc., which is not entirely out of the question when it comes to fire.

The earth is labeled "dchdy", which can be transcribed as follows:

"d"	"ch"	"d"	"y"
d/t	consonant + vowel	d/t	abbreviation

Admittedly, the meaning in this case is not very clear. Alchemists, however, assigned elements to different parts of matter according to the behavior. The parts falling in the solution to the bottom of vessel, i.e. the insoluble precipitates, were called earth.⁹

The transcription could then be as follows:

"d"	"ch"	"d"	"y"
d	(e)	ci	d abbreviation

Of all the four labels of elements, this label has the least straightforward interpretation of its meaning. One letter is probably missing. If we accept the possibility that the letter was deliberately omitted in order to obscure the meaning of the label, then in view of the above (the earth as a descending part of the matter) a connection with the word decido, i.e. to fall [78], can be considered.

It has already been mentioned that the arrangement of the elements in the drawing is such that the elements sharing the moisture principle are on the left (air, water), the elements sharing the dryness principle are on the right (fire, earth), and the empty mouth of tube (without label), corresponding to the quintessence, is located in the middle. It is noteworthy that the label "olkchs" seems to correspond to this arrangement. The character "k" ("q" in Latin) is located in the middle of the label, just like the quintessence in the drawing. The left side of the label, i.e. "ol" ("vowel+m" in Latin), corresponds to the beginning of the word umidum (wet) or umiditas (humidity). The right side of the label, i.e. "chs", corresponds to the reversed beginning of the word siccitas (drought) or siccus (dry). Here, the "sch" in Voynichese could be "sic" or "scc" in Latin.

The following assignment of characters can be assumed.

Voynichese	Latin
o	a (generally a vowel or multiple vowels), consonant if standing before consonant
a	e (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
l	m
ch	c, t, ce, ta (generally consonant+vowel), vowel+vowel, consonant+consonant
e	c, t, substituting character
d	d, t
r	r
k	q
y	abbreviation character
f	p
t	l
s	s

⁹ However, the concept of assigning motion to elements is much older, see e.g. *De caelo* by Aristotle [79]: "... ignis enim rectis lineis superiora capebit, terrena autem pondere suo deorsum mouentur ad medium..." ("...fire moving straight upward and earthy bodies moving with their weight straight downward towards the centre...").

2.6. Plant root

The fact that the root in f102r2 is identical to the root in f18v is already known [80,81]. However, we want to focus our attention on the label "koldarod" above the root drawing in f102r2 (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Plant root at the bottom of f102r2. Credit: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Yale University.

Considering the assumed meaning of the characters, the label can be transcribed as follows

"k" "o" "l" "d" "a" "r" "o" "d"
 q u o m (o) d o r a d (...)

resulting in two words quomodo rad... (rado, radere [82]), i.e. how to scrape (the root). The f102r2 belongs to the pharmaceutical section, in which descriptions of plant processing procedures are (quite reasonably) expected. The above-mentioned meaning of the label "koldarod" does not contradict this assumption.

2.7. Moons on f67r2

Special coincidences can be found in the case of the labels of moons on f67r2. These are twelve words placed in a circular band bounded by lines, with just one word below each of the moons (Fig. 6).

These words are as follows: okadar, qotoear, dchodar, ysaldal, ytodal, toldaiin, otardy, chodalg, ytchody, yochthys, ytokar, and otolor.

Fig. 6. Detail of f67r2 with twelve moons. Credit: Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, Yale University.

There is a possibility that these are the names of the months, i.e. January (ianuarius), February (februarius), March (martius), April (aprilis), May (maius), June (iunius), July (iulius), August (augustus), September (septembris), October (octobris), November (novembris), and December (decembris), while the order of course may be different.

None of the words in Voynichese match any month name in Latin. However, let's try the following procedure and see what result it will lead to.

Let's sort the words in Voynichese in a row without spaces

okadarqotoeardchodarysaldalytodaltoldaiinotardychodalgytchodyyochthsytokarotolor (1)

and do the same with the names of the months in Latin

ianuariusfebruariusmartiusaprilismaiusiuniusiuliusaugustusseptembrisoctobrisnovembrisdecembris (2)

Assuming that the character "y" in Voynichese can be used instead of -is, -us, -ius, etc., we mark all "y" in line (1), mark the corresponding number of suffixes in line (2) starting from left

okadarqotoeardchodarysaldalytodaltoldaiinotardychodalgytchodyyochthsytokarotolor
ianuariiusfebruariiusmartiusaprilismaiuusiuniusiuliusaugustusseptembrisoctobrisnovembrisdecembris

and remove the marked characters and letters. We obtain the following two lines and it is remarkable that the same number (72) of characters/letters remained in each line.

Voynichese: okadarqotoeardchodarsaldaltoldaldaiinotardchodalgtchodocthstokarotolor
 Latin: ianuarfebruarmartaprilmaiuniulaugustseptembrisoctobrisnovembrisdecembris

Let's have two more assumptions. The first assumption is that "qo" in the word "qotoear" is the prefix "ap" in the word "aprilis". There is no other prefix of this type in the names of the months in Latin and also "qo" occurs only once in Voynichese.¹⁰

The second assumption is that the four times occurring "ch" in Voynichese corresponds to "fe", "se", "co" and "ce" in Latin.

The pair of lines now looks as follows and it is very interesting that in both Voynichese and Latin names of months there is just one case where there is one other character between "c" and "h" (Voynichese) and "c" and "o" (Latin):

Voynichese: okadard~~q~~o~~e~~ard~~ch~~odarsaldaltoldaldaiinotard~~ch~~odalgt~~ch~~odo~~ct~~hstokarotolor
 Latin: ianuar~~f~~e~~b~~ruarmart~~a~~p~~r~~ilmaiuniulaugust~~s~~e~~p~~tembris~~o~~c~~t~~obrisnovembrisde~~c~~e~~m~~bris

The marked letters will be removed and we will also remove the letters lying between "c" and "h" in Voynichese and between "c" and "o" in Latin (i.e. "cth" and "cto", respectively, is removed). Two following lines are obtained, each containing 61 characters/letters.

Voynichese: okadartoear~~d~~o~~d~~arsaldaltoldaldaiinotardodalgt~~o~~dstokarotolor
 Latin: ianuar~~b~~ruarmar~~t~~rilm~~a~~iuniulaugust~~p~~tembris~~o~~brisnovembris~~d~~embris

As already mentioned, the character "d" in Voynichese could correspond to the letters "d" and "t" in Latin. The number of characters "d" in Voynichese (9 characters) does not match the number of letters "d" and "t" in Latin (a total of 4 letters). However, the agreement is found when assuming that the character "d" in Voynichese corresponds not only to "d" and "t", but also to "b" in Latin (a total of 9 letters):

Voynichese: oka~~d~~artoear~~d~~o~~d~~arsaldaltoldaldaiinotard~~d~~odalgt~~o~~dstokarotolor
 Latin: ianuar~~b~~ruarmar~~t~~rilm~~a~~iuniulaugust~~p~~tembris~~o~~brisnovembris~~d~~embris

By removing the marked characters and letters, we get the following two lines, each containing 52 characters/letters.

¹⁰ The author made this assumption only on the basis of the described procedure and only subsequently discovered that quite similar relationship, i.e. "qo" = "apo", had already been proposed earlier on the basis of computer analyses comparing the frequencies of characters in the MS with Latin n-grams [83].

Voynichese: okaartoearoarsalaltoaltolaiinotaralgtoostokarotolor

Latin: ianuarruarmarrilmaiuniulauguspemrisorisnovemrisemris

Let's continue by dividing each line into vowels and consonants. We assume that "o", "a" and "ii" in Voynichese are vowels, the character "e" in Voynichese will be considered a consonant.

Voynichese vowels: oaaaoaaoaoaiioaoaoaoao

Voynichese consonants: krterrsltltlnrlgtstkrtr

Latin vowels: iauauaaiuiuaueioioeiei

Latin consonants: nrrmrrlmnlgsprsrsvmrsmrs

Assuming that "ii" from the word "toldaiin" in Voynichese represents one vowel, then we get 26 vowels in Voynichese and 26 vowels in Latin.

There are consonants left, of which there are 26 in Voynichese and 28 in Latin. We assume that "l", "r", "s" and "t" in Voynichese is "m", "r", "s" and "l" in Latin, respectively.

There are six "l" in Voynichese and five "m" in Latin.

Voynichese: krterrllllllnrlgtstkrllr

Latin: nrrmrrllmnlgspmrsrsnvmrsmrs

There are six "r" in Voynichese and nine "r" in Latin.

Voynichese: krrterrrrsltltlnrlgtstkrrtr

Latin: nrrrrmrrllmnlgspmrrrsrnvmrscmrs

There are two "s" in Voynichese and five "s" in Latin.

Voynichese: krterrslltltlnrlgtstkrtr

Latin: nrrmrrlmnlgspmrsrsnvmrscmrs

There are seven "t" in Voynichese and two "l" in Latin.

Voynichese: krtterrlllttlnrlgtstkrtr

Latin: nrrmrrllmnlgspmrsrsnvmrscmrs

The number of characters/letters for each pair "l" – "m", "r" – "r", "s" – "s" and "t" – "l" does not match, however, the total number of "l", "r", "s" and "t" in Voynichese is 21 and the total number of "m", "r", "s" and "l" in Latin is 21.

By removing "l", "r", "s" and "t" in Voynichese and "m", "r", "s" and "l" in Latin we get the following two lines.

Voynichese: kengk

Latin: nngpnvc

It is interesting that there is the "e" among the remaining characters in Voynichese and the "c" among the remaining characters in Latin. In accordance with the f68r3 (see 2.1. section), the "e" in Voynichese could be "c" in Latin.

By removing these characters we get the following two lines:

Voynichese: kngk

Latin: nngpnv

In these last two lines, there are no further clues for assigning individual characters from Voynichese to individual characters from Latin, and therefore we will not attempt to do so. Fewer characters in Voynichese compared to Latin support the theory that the MS is abbreviated and some letters are omitted.

Where did this procedure lead us? The results point to the possibility that the labels of moons were created by randomly mixing letters from the names of months in Latin. We have no idea why the author of the MS would do it this way, we cannot explain it and we will not look for an explanation. However, the multiple match of the number of characters, as shown in this section, seems too conspicuous to be a coincidence.

The following assignment of characters can be assumed.

Voynichese	Latin
o	a (generally a vowel or multiple vowels), consonant if standing before consonant
a	e (generally a vowel or multiple vowels)
l	m
ch	c, t, ce, ta (generally consonant+vowel), vowel+vowel, consonant+consonant
e	c, t, substituting character
d	d, t
r	r
k	q
y	abbreviation character
f	p
t	l
qo	ap

It is worth noting the correspondence of characters in the word "qotoear" with letters in the word "aprilis". The reader remembers that the first assumption was that "qo" is "ap", and it has been shown that "t", "r" and "e" in Voynichese could be "l", "r" and "c" in Latin. Thus, the word "qotoear" can be transcribed to "apl(wovel)c(wovel)r" and by changing the position of characters we get "apr(wovel)l(wovel)c", i.e. "aprilic". The similarity with the word "aprilis" is

considerable, but since no similar result can be obtained for other labels of moons, we will consider this to be a mere (albeit strange) coincidence.

3. Stems of flowers

The noun *stem* is *coles, colis [m.]* in Latin. With regard to the characters identified above, it can be assumed that the corresponding words in Voynichese will contain characters meaning the letter c, the letter l, the letter s or the letter m (singular accusative *colem*, plural genitive *colum*), some vowels and probably also the abbreviation character "y". Let's try to create such words and see in which sections of the MS they occur. The words should be found mostly in the botanical section. This is the hypothesis we want to confirm or disprove. The voynichese.com web page [14] is used to determine the number of occurrences of individual variants in the MS.

Let's keep the assumption that the character "t" in Voynichese is "l" in Latin. So a simple transcription of the Latin word *coles* would be "eotas" or "chotas". However, these words do not occur in the MS, just as the words "eotos", "chotos", "eatos", "chatos", "eatas", "chatas" do not occur there.

If we accept the possibility that the character "ch" in Voynichese is "consonant+vowel" in Latin, we can transcribe the word *coles* as "chts" ("chtas" does not occur in the MS). The word "chts" appears only 1×, on a folio belonging to the astronomical section (Table 1; for detailed data see also Table 2). This is not a very encouraging result, but let's move on. Another variant is "ctos" ("ctas" does not occur in the MS). This word appears 2×, on folios belonging to the botanical section (Tables 1, 2). This already looks better. Let's try the variant "cthos" ("cthas" does not occur in the MS). This word occurs 1× (Tables 1, 2), on a folio belonging to the botanical section. This is a satisfactory result.

Now come the variants ending in a vowel (singular dative *coli*, singular ablative *cole*), i.e. "chto", "chta", "cto", "cta", "ctho" and "ctha". Of these variants, "cto", "ctho", "ctha" can be found in the MS, and all three, without exception, are found only on the folios of the botanical section (Tables 1, 2).

The variant "cth" occurs 5×, and only in the botanical section (Tables 1, 2). The variant "cht" does not occur in the MS.

There are six variants ending in "l" (i.e. "m" in Latin; singular accusative *colem*, plural genitive *colum*): "cthol", "cthal", "ctol", "ctal", "chtol", "chtal". Of these, only "ctal" does not occur in

the MS. The variant "ctol" occurs 2× and in both cases on the folios of the botanical section (Tables 1, 2). The variant "cthol" occurs 60×, of which the overwhelming majority (49 times) is on the folios of the botanical section and 6×, 3×, and 2× on the folios of the pharmaceutical, text and biological (also referred to as balneological) section, respectively (Tables 1, 2). The variant "cthal" occurs 7×, of which 5× on the folios of the botanical section, 1× and 1× on the folios of the text and biological section, respectively (Tables 1, 2). The variant "chtol" occurs 5×, of which 3× on the folios of the botanical section, 1× and 1× on the folios of the text and biological section, respectively (Tables 1, 2). The variant "chtal" occurs 6×, of which 4× on the folios of the text section, 1× and 1× on the folios of the botanical and biological section, respectively (Tables 1, 2).

Variants containing the abbreviation character "y" remain: "cty", "chty", "cthy".

The variant "cty" occurs 5×, and only on the folios of the botanical section (Tables 1, 2).

The variant "chty" occurs 13×, of which 7× on the folios of the botanical section and 1×, 3×, and 2× on the folios of the pharmaceutical, text, and biological section, respectively (Tables 1, 2). The variant "cthy" occurs 110 times, overwhelmingly (97 times) on the folios of the botanical section, and 3×, 5×, 1× and 4× on the folios of the pharmaceutical, text, biological, and astronomical section, respectively (Tables 1, 2).

There are a total of 237 occurrences of the aforementioned variants in the MS, of which the vast majority (197 occurrences) are on the folios of the botanical section, and 17, 10, 8 and 5 occurrences on the folios of the text, pharmaceutical, biological, and astronomical section, respectively (Tables 1, 2).

With the exception of "chtos" and "chtal", all variants show a dominant occurrence in the botanical section (Tables 1, 2). This is a negligible deviation, as "chtos" and "chtal" occur only seven times in the MS, which is 2.95% of all 237 occurrences of all variants.

Moreover, the highest occurrence of "chtal" (4 out of 6) is in the text section, the content of which can only be estimated. If these are the recipes, as some authors believe, then this cannot be considered a significant deviation.

Let's summarize the achieved results. We have created variants that we believe may correspond to the word stem. Our hypothesis was that the word stem should be found primarily in the botanical section. A total of 237 occurrences of the aforementioned variants can be found in the MS (Tables 1, 2). We found that of this number, 197 occurrences are in the botanical section (Tables 1, 2). The botanical section therefore contains 83.12% of all occurrences of variants (Table 1), which sufficiently supports the initial hypothesis.

Table 1

Fifteen predicted variants of the word *coles, colis [m.]* (stem in Latin) are listed in the first column. The second column indicates the number of occurrences of each variant in the entire MS (N). The third to seventh columns show the percentage of the occurrence of a given variant in individual sections of the MS – botanical (bot), pharmaceutical (pharm), text (text), biological (bio) and astronomical (astro). The scribe column (notation according to Davis [4]) shows which scribes wrote the folios of the MS on which the variant is found. The last column shows language (A or B according to Currier [16]) on folios with the occurrence of given variant.

variant	N	bot (%)	pharm (%)	text (%)	bio (%)	astro (%)	scribe	Currier language
"chts"	1	0	0	0	0	100	4	-
"ctos"	2	100	0	0	0	0	1	A
"cthos"	1	100	0	0	0	0	1	A
"cto"	4	100	0	0	0	0	1	A
"ctho"	15	100	0	0	0	0	1	A
"ctha"	1	100	0	0	0	0	1	A
"cth"	5	100	0	0	0	0	1	A,B
"ctol"	2	100	0	0	0	0	1	A,B
"cthol"	60	81.66	10	5	3.33	0	1,2,3	A,B
"cthal"	7	71.43	0	14.29	14.29	0	1,2	A,B
"chtol"	5	60	0	20	20	0	1,2,3	A,B
"chtal"	6	16.66	0	66.66	16.66	0	1,2,3	B
"cty"	5	100	0	0	0	0	1	A
"chty"	13	53.85	7.69	23.08	15.38	0	1,2,3,5	A,B
"cthy"	110	88.18	2.73	4.54	0.91	3.64	1,2,3,4	A,B
all	237	83.12	4.22	7.17	3.38	2.11	1,2,3,4,5	A,B

The occurrence of individual variants on the folios was compared with the scribes of the folios as recognized by Davis [4]. For each variant, the last column of Table 1 lists the scribes (notation according to [4]) who wrote the folios on which the variant is found (for a detailed overview, the reader is referred to Table 2). The dominance of scribe 1 is determined by the dominance of this scribe in the entire MS. Overall, it can be stated that no scribe uses only one variant.

As for the Currier languages A and B [16,84], the variants are mostly found in Currier A, but not limited to it (Table 1). Table 1 shows an interesting fact. These are two variants ("chts" and "chtal") occurring dominantly in a section other than the botanical section. In the first case ("chts"), it is a folio with an undetermined language. In the second case ("chtal"), it is exclusively the Currier B.

The results indicate that there is a word (in several variants) that is characteristic for one section. Further research should be aimed at identifying additional words specific to different sections (e.g. "chos" for pharmaceutical section, "chor" for botanical and pharmaceutical section, "olkol" for biological section, etc.). To the author's knowledge, similar research has not yet been performed.

Table 2

Number of occurrences of each of the fifteen predicted variants of the word *coles, colis* [*m.*] (stem in Latin) on MS folios (folios without occurrence of any variant are not included). The first and the second column indicates the language (A or B according to Currier [16]) and the scribe (1-5 according to Davis [4]), respectively. The third column indicates which section the folio belongs to – botanical (bot), pharmaceutical (pharm), text (text), biological (bio) and astronomical (astro). The fourth column indicates the folio. The last column indicates the total number of occurrences of different variants on the given folio.

		scribes																
		1,2,3	1,2	1	1,2,3	1,2,3	1,2,3,4	1	1,2,3,5	1	1	4	1	1	1	1		
Currier	scribe	type	folio	cthol	cthal	ctol	ctol	cthal	cthy	cty	cty	cthos	ctos	ctos	ctho	ctha	cth	cto
A	1	text	1r	1	1				3									5
A	1	bot	1v	2					2									4
A	1	bot	2r						2							1		3
A	1	bot	2v							1								1
A	1	bot	3r	2					2									4
A	1	bot	3v		1				1									2
A	1	bot	4r	2					2									4
A	1	bot	4v	1					1								1	3
A	1	bot	5r						2									2
A	1	bot	6r						3									3
A	1	bot	6v	3					3									6
A	1	bot	7r	1														1
A	1	bot	7v	1					2									3
A	1	bot	8r						1					1				2
A	1	bot	8v	1						1								2
A	1	bot	9r						5									5
A	1	bot	9v						1	1								2
A	1	bot	10r						3	1				1		1		6
A	1	bot	10v						1									1
A	1	bot	11r						4									4
A	1	bot	11v											1				1
A	1	bot	14v						2									2
A	1	bot	15r						5									5
A	1	bot	15v						4									4
A	1	bot	16r						1									1
A	1	bot	16v						1									1
A	1	bot	17r						1									1
A	1	bot	17v	2					1									3
A	1	bot	18r	2	1				2									5
A	1	bot	19v	2														2
A	1	bot	20v						2									2
A	1	bot	21r						2									2
A	1	bot	21v				1		1	1				1				4
A	1	bot	22r	1					2									3
A	1	bot	22v						4									4
A	1	bot	23v	1										1				2
A	1	bot	24r	1	2				1									4
A	1	bot	24v														1	1
A	1	bot	27r											1				1

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